

THE STATE OF PRACTICE OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' MANAGEMENT CULTURE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15799427>

Abstract. *The laws of societal development encompass both general patterns and natural regularities. In many cases, rather than seeking entirely new pathways, adopting ready-made models from developed countries and applying them creatively can yield more effective results. Based on this understanding, significant attention is now being paid to the application of internationally tested innovative experiences that play a crucial role in advancing the production sectors of the national economy.*

Keywords: *development regularities, scientific approach, model adoption, competence, innovation process management, managerial activity, organization of educational activities, system of managerial knowledge, development of professional competencies.*

There are general aspects and natural laws in the laws of development of society and rather than searching for new, specific ways in this regard, sometimes it is better to take ready-made templates from developed countries and use them creatively. Based on this, today, serious attention is paid to the application of innovative experiences tested in international experience in economic sectors and of great importance in the development of the production sectors of the country's economy.

In order to study the practical state of development of students' managerial culture, the curriculum of the subject "Fundamentals of Educational Management" for the direction 60112500 - School Management was analyzed in the research work: in the 2022-2023 academic year, during the 3-4th semester, only 150 hours of classroom training and 150 hours of independent study are allocated, and the total workload is 300 hours.

60112500 – The curriculum of the subject “Fundamentals of Educational Management” for the School Management major states that Content of the subject.

The purpose of teaching the subject is to form in students a system of knowledge and professional competencies in the management of innovative processes, international assessment programs, and the organization and management of educational work, which are the foundations of school management.

The task of the subject: to teach the theoretical and practical foundations of managing innovation processes; to form skills in managing international assessment programs, including PISA; to develop skills in organizing, conducting educational events, and monitoring spiritual and educational work.

The following topics are of great importance in developing the managerial culture of students:

Current issues of education and innovative educational policy

Current issues of general secondary education and ways to solve them. Issues of vocational education and innovations. Additional education, innovative approaches to its organization. Innovative educational policy: essence, main directions, implementation mechanisms. Principles

of managing pedagogical innovations. Modernization and experimentation in education.

Theoretical and methodological foundations of monitoring the quality of education.

General approaches to studying education systems. Methodological foundations of studying the quality of education. Education as an object of systematic analysis and modeling. Education quality management as a field of scientific knowledge and practice. Planning education quality. Innovative features of education quality monitoring. Designing the education quality monitoring process.

State guarantees for ensuring the quality of education.

State system of education quality management. Standardization of education - a guarantee and condition for ensuring high quality of education. State education standard in the system of continuous education. State education standards - a normative basis for managing the quality of education. Quality of professional training of personnel and their competitiveness.

Education quality management.

Interaction of educational institutions with the external environment and social organizations. Socio-pedagogical structure of an educational institution and the results of its activities. Systematic planning of educational institutions and education quality management processes. Control over the activities of an educational institution. Forms and methods of public administration.

Self-government at school.

Conditions for self-government and its development in the student community. Stages of self-government in the student community. Tasks of self-government in the student community. The structure of self-government in the student community. Levels of self-government of students in middle and senior grades. The composition and powers of self-government of students at school. The composition and powers of the class self-government body. The model of self-government of the student community. Planning the work of self-government bodies of students. Conditions for creating a systematic and continuous system of self-government of the student community.

Technology for resolving pedagogical conflicts.

Causes of conflict situations. Peculiarities of pedagogical conflicts. Innovative pedagogical conflicts. Conflicts arising in educational activities. Conflictological culture of the teacher. Conflictological competence of students. Dynamics of conflict development. Pedagogical conflict management. Mediation technology.

Peculiarities of managing educational work at school

The essence and principles of managing the educational process. Types of management functions and their brief description (information-analytical, motivational-targeted, planned-prognostic, organizational-executive, control-diagnostic, regulatory-corrective). Peculiarities of the management activities of the subjects of the educational process (director, deputy director for academic work, deputy director for spiritual-moral and youth work, class teacher).

Also, based on the objectives and stages of the research, the syllabus of the subject “Fundamentals of School Management” for the direction 60112500 – School Management was analyzed.

The syllabus of this subject states that a future manager studying in the educational direction “Fundamentals of School Management” must have knowledge, skills and qualifications in organizing and managing innovative processes at school, designing innovative processes, effectively implementing innovative activities, managing international assessment programs,

managing the quality of education based on the PISA and TIMSS programs, organizing and managing educational work.

This program includes national and world pedagogical sources, their study by eras, and leading pedagogical ideas.

The purpose of teaching the subject is to equip future school managers with knowledge, skills and qualifications related to educational management.

The task of the subject is to identify, analyze and teach the laws, principles, methods and techniques of educational management and use them in a seminar.

Within the framework of the tasks carried out in the process of mastering the academic subject "Fundamentals of School Management", the student:

Create a basis for the formation of pedagogical and managerial thinking;

Master regional and foreign scientific and pedagogical experiences in managing the educational process;

Develop the ability to manage the educational process;

Make appropriate decisions in accordance with the priority laws and principles of management in education;

Study innovative directions in the organization of management.

Initial knowledge necessary for mastering the subject: to teach students the basics of personnel management in education, personnel departments and their functions in the education management system, personnel, information, technical and legal support of the personnel management system, functional division of labor in education, methods of planning and analyzing the development of personnel potential of education systems, methods of transitions in the education system, working with reserves, methods of selecting pedagogical personnel.

In order to study the practical situation of developing students' managerial culture, the issues of management of general secondary schools were also studied.

The effectiveness of the activities of general secondary schools depends on the effectiveness of the activities of several, both independent and directly and indirectly interconnected and related, subjects (managers) and objects (managed). Therefore, the activities of general secondary schools can be viewed as the interconnected activities of subjects and objects, that is, leaders and educational processes. In this approach, the activities of leaders, teachers and students, specialists and other employees are considered as a system of subject activities, and the activities of educational institutions and educational processes are considered as a system of object activities, the effectiveness of their activities has an impact on the effectiveness of the activities of the general secondary education system, which is a complex pedagogical system.

General secondary education processes are a complex process in themselves, the set of which forms a holistic system, and the coordination of the activities of this complex pedagogical system, in turn, requires the implementation of innovative approaches to management. One of the most basic and important functions of management in the processes of coordination and management of the activities of general secondary schools is planning, the objectivity of which affects not only the effectiveness of the activities of a particular educational institution, but also the effectiveness of the activities of general secondary schools as a whole. The level of improvement of the activities of general secondary schools depends not only on the scientific potential of its subjects of activity, but also on the perfection of the developed strategy of the educational institution, the correct selection of tactics, as well as on the fact that the general

strategy developed in accordance with strategic goals is aimed at ensuring the continuity of the activities of all components of the system. This connection and integration represent the importance of strategic management in the management of general secondary education schools.

Also, the subject of strategic management is the systematic, strategic, structural, situational, corporate, functional, integrated, diversified approaches used to improve the processes of organizing and managing the activities of general secondary education schools, as well as methods and mechanisms for designing, modeling, collecting information, analyzing and objectively evaluating, motivating according to strategic goals.

The development of long-term strategies that serve the development of general secondary education schools, finding effective solutions to issues related to the successful implementation of the strategy to achieve the strategic goal, as the main functional tasks of strategic management, play an important role in managing the general secondary education system. Indeed, an excellent strategy in the management processes of general secondary education schools and its successful implementation serve the development of the activities of this system.

The program for improving the processes of organizing and managing the activities of general secondary schools consists of a set of perspective plans that implement the development of one or all components of the system. In this regard, the functional tasks of strategic management are:

- to develop plans with a defined goal and strategic direction, with predetermined effectiveness and prospects;

- to design based on the study of the characteristics of the processes serving the activities of general secondary schools;

- to develop mechanisms for implementing special, integrated, functional and diversification approaches that serve as a basis for the development of management processes;

- to create mechanisms for using special and advanced technologies in the development and implementation of development strategies;

- to identify the development trends of educational processes, to formulate perspective strategic plans that correspond to existing opportunities and general goals, and to improve them according to circumstances;

- design motivation processes that form interests in all subjects in the effectiveness of activities carried out according to common strategic goals;

- develop models of management processes with an innovative structure that ensure the efficiency of general secondary education processes;

- model the processes of implementing technologies and mechanisms for the effective implementation of strategic plans developed to achieve efficiency and improve them.

The literature also emphasizes the importance of the following conditions for managing general secondary schools based on strategic management:

- implement the integration of management technologies and mechanisms of general secondary schools with the management technologies and mechanisms of the continuous education system;

- ensure the coherence and continuity of the content of extracurricular education with general secondary education and specialized educational programs;

- ensure that the organizational structure of management subjects is convenient for development based on adapting it to the functions and structures of educational institutions that

are the objects of management.

Therefore, the development of students' managerial culture is of great importance, based on the real needs of the labor market, individual structural elements of academic disciplines, and the need for modernized management of general secondary education.

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